

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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FACTORS MOTIVATING UZBEK LEARNERS OF ENGLISH IN THE UPPER GRADE

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Abstract: *The article explores intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors that influence student engagement and success demonstrating key motivational drivers, the role of parents and teachers, peer influence, personality differences between introverts and extroverts, and the integration of digital tools in language learning. Motivation plays a crucial role in language acquisition, particularly for students learning English as a foreign language in Uzbekistan. By analyzing these motivational factors, this study offers insights into optimizing English language instruction to cater to diverse student needs.*

Key words and expressions: *Intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, student engagement, peer influence, introverted learners, extroverted learners, learning environment, constructive feedback, interactive learning, digital tools, cultural exposure, self-placed learning, bilingual education, collaborative learning, self-determination.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada asosiy motivatsiya omillari tahlil etilib, ota-ona, o'qituvchilarning roli, tengdoshlar ta'siri, introvert va ekstravert shaxslar o'rtasidagi shaxslararo farqlar hamda raqamli vositalarning til o'rganishga integratsiyasi o'rganiladi. Motivatsiya tilni egallash jarayonida hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, ayniqsa*

O'zbekistonda Ingliz tilini chet til sifatida o'rganayotgan talabalar uchun juda muhim hisoblanadi. Mazkur tadqiqot motivatsiya omillarini tahlil etish orqali Ingliz tilini o'qitishni turli talabalar ehtiyojlariga mos ravishda optimallashtirish usullarini yoritadi.

Tayanch so'z va iboralar: *Ichki motivatsiya, tashqi motivatsiya, talabalar faolligi, tengdoshlar ta'siri, introvert o'quvchilar, ekstravert o'quvchilar, o'quv muhiti, konstruktiv fikr-mulohaza, interaktiv o'qitish, raqamli vositalar, madaniy muhit bilan tanishish, mustaqil o'rganish tizimi, ikki tilli ta'lim, collaborative learning, o'zini tarbiyalash va rivojlantirish.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются внутренние и внешние мотивационные факторы, которые влияют на вовлеченность и успех учащихся, демонстрируя ключевые мотивационные факторы, роль родителей и учителей, влияние сверстников, различия в личности между интровертами и экстравертами и интеграцию цифровых инструментов в изучение языка. Мотивация играет решающую роль в освоении языка, особенно для учащихся, изучающих английский как иностранный язык в Узбекистане. Анализируя эти мотивационные факторы, это исследование предлагает идеи по оптимизации обучения английскому языку для удовлетворения различных потребностей учащихся.*

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Ключевые слова и выражения: Внутренняя мотивация, внешняя мотивация, вовлеченность учащихся, влияние сверстников, интровертированные учащиеся, экстравертированные учащиеся, учебная среда, конструктивная обратная связь, интерактивное обучение, цифровые инструменты, культурное воздействие, самостоятельное обучение, двуязычное образование, совместное обучение, самоопределение.

Introduction: In an increasingly globalized world, learning foreign languages has become essential for professional and academic success. On

May 6, 2020, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired a video conference meeting focused on improving the foreign language education system in Uzbekistan. Recognizing the growing demand for multilingual specialists, the government introduced initiatives such as specialized language schools, updated curricula and new teaching methodologies. However, infrastructure alone is insufficient—students need motivation to fully engage in learning English. This paper examines various motivational factors that influence students' enthusiasm for learning English.

Literature review: Motivation is a fundamental element in second language acquisition (SLA) research. Gardner R.C. and Lambert W.E. (1972) pioneered studies on motivation, categorizing it into instrumental motivation (learning a language for practical purposes, such as career advancement) and integrative motivation (learning a language to integrate into a community or culture). These concepts remain relevant today as students' motivations vary depending on personal goals, societal expectations, and educational structures. Ryan Richard M. and Deci Edward L.'s Self-Determination Theory (2000) further classifies motivation into intrinsic (internal drive and enjoyment) and extrinsic (external rewards and pressures). This framework provides insights into how parental encouragement, teacher involvement, and external rewards influence Uzbek students' engagement in English learning. Parental and teacher involvement is crucial in fostering student motivation. Studies show that students who receive consistent parental encouragement perform better in language learning (Noels K.A., Pelletier L.G., Clément R. & Vallerand R.J., 2000). Parents' attitudes towards English significantly impact students' willingness to learn, especially in societies where English is seen as a key to career opportunities. Similarly, teacher motivation strategies play a critical role. Dörnyei Z. (2001) highlights that effective teachers foster student autonomy, competence, and relatedness, making lessons

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engaging and relevant. In Uzbekistan, where educational reforms prioritize modern teaching methodologies, understanding these motivational techniques can enhance English language education. Social constructivist theories emphasize peer interaction in language learning (Vygotsky Lev, 1978). The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) suggests that learners progress faster when assisted by more proficient peers or teachers. This aligns with studies on peer influence, where students surrounded by motivated classmates exhibit higher engagement levels (Brown D.N., 2007). However, peer dynamics can also have negative effects, such as reliance on the native language during group work or fear of making mistakes. Educators should balance group activities to maximize constructive peer interaction without compromising the focus on English proficiency. Personality traits influence language learning success. According to Eysenck H.J.'s (2016) extraversion-introversion theory, extroverts thrive in social and interactive settings, while introverts prefer independent study. Dörnyei Z. (2000) argues that adaptive teaching strategies are essential to cater to both personality types. • Introverts benefit from self-paced learning, writing activities, and small-group discussions.

- Extroverts thrive in debates, role-playing, and real-life communication practice.

Understanding these individual differences allows educators to tailor instructional approaches for optimal learning outcomes.

The integration of digital tools in education has transformed motivation in language learning. Studies by Warschauer Mark (1996) indicate that technology-enhanced language learning increases student engagement. Gamified platforms like Duolingo, Kahoot, and Memrise provide interactive and enjoyable learning experiences, reinforcing both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. C.R. Graham's Additionally, "Blended

Learning Approaches" (2006) combining face-to-face instruction with online learning have proven effective in maintaining student interest and improving language retention. In Uzbekistan, the adoption of digital tools in English instruction aligns with global best practices, making it an essential factor in sustaining student motivation.

This literature review underscores the multifaceted nature of motivation in second language learning. Factors such as parental and teacher support, peer influence, personality differences, and technological integration all contribute to student engagement. Drawing from research in SLA theories, psychology, and

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educational technology, this study provides a comprehensive framework for understanding and enhancing motivation among Uzbek learners of English.

Topicality of the research. The global significance of English as a lingua franca has heightened the necessity of effective language learning, especially in non-native contexts like Uzbekistan. The motivation of learners plays a crucial role in the successful acquisition of English. Understanding the specific factors that influence motivation in Uzbek learners is essential for developing tailored educational strategies, thereby enhancing their language proficiency. This research focuses on motivational dynamics in upper-grade students in Uzbekistan.

The aim of this research is to identify and analyze the key factors that motivate upper-grade Uzbek learners in their English language acquisition, providing insights for educators to enhance teaching practices and learner outcomes.

The novelty of the research includes the unique socio-cultural and educational context of Uzbekistan, offering a comprehensive analysis of motivational factors from the learners' perspective. This research delves into the intersection of cultural influences, educational environment, and individual learner characteristics in the Uzbek context.

Methods of the research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methodologies. This approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of motivational factors. The mixed-methods design is chosen to capture both the breadth and depth of learner experiences, providing detailed analysis of the motivational landscape.

Content of the research. Motivation is the driving force behind learning and achievement. Richard M. Ryan and Edward L. Deci categorize motivation into:

- *Intrinsic motivation – Driven by personal interest and enjoyment of learning.*
- *Extrinsic motivation – Influenced by external rewards such as grades, parental expectations, or career prospects.*

A student's motivation can be significantly shaped by their interaction with parents, teachers, and their learning environment.

1. Parental and Teacher Influence on Motivation

The support and expectations of parents and teachers play a vital role in fostering student motivation. Key factors include:

- *Parents showing consistent interest in their child's academic progress;*
- *Teachers regularly updating parents on student achievements and areas for improvement;*

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- *Setting high but realistic expectations and providing students with time and resources to study.*

Effective communication between teachers, students, and parents creates an environment for learners' acquisition.

2. Peer Influence and Learning Environment

a) Students are often motivated by their peers. A dynamic learning environment can have positive effects:

- *Provide more speaking practice opportunities;*
- *Foster a comfortable and pressure-free learning atmosphere;*
- *Enable constructive peer corrections;*
- *Enhance cultural exposure through interactions with advanced learners.*

b) Students are often motivated by their peers. A dynamic learning environment can have negative effects:

- *Encourage excessive socialization over learning.*
- *Lead to reliance on the native language instead of English.*
- *Cause fear of mistakes, discouraging active participation.*

A balanced approach—where teachers guide students toward productive peer interactions—ensures optimal learning outcomes.

3. Personality Differences in Learning Motivation

Motivating Introverted Learners

- *Personalized learning with self-paced materials.*
- *Writing activities like journaling or essays.*
- *Small group discussions to reduce anxiety.*
- *Digital learning tools for private practice.*
- *Encouraging participation without overwhelming pressure.*

Motivating Extroverted Learners

- *Debates, role-playing, and presentations.*
- *Group activities to maintain engagement.*
- *Gamified learning experiences.*
- *Real-life practice with native speakers.*
- *Positive reinforcement through rewards and recognition.*

4. Technology as a Motivational Tool

Incorporating technology in language education enhances engagement and motivation. Modern digital tools include:

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- *Interactive apps – Platforms like Duolingo and Memrise gamify language learning.*

- *Gamification elements – Quiz-based tools like Kahoot encourage competition and engagement.*

- *Virtual simulations – AI-driven chatbots and speech recognition software improve fluency.*

By incorporating technology, educators can create an interactive and enjoyable learning environment for students.

Motivation in language learning is a complex interplay of internal and external factors. While government initiatives provide a solid foundation, students' success ultimately depends on the role of parents, teachers, peers, and personalized learning approaches. Understanding the needs of both introverted and extroverted learners allows educators to create inclusive classrooms that foster motivation. Additionally, the integration of modern technology enhances engagement and offers diverse learning opportunities. A comprehensive approach that includes parental support, interactive methodologies, and digital resources ensures that Uzbek-English learners remain motivated and achieve proficiency in the language.

There are many positive factors to preparing lessons with peers:

1. **More Practice Opportunities:** Speaking with friends in the target language helps improve fluency;

2. **Comfortable Learning Environment:** Students feel less pressure when practicing with friends;

3. **Peer Corrections:** Friends can correct mistakes in a supportive way;

4. **Cultural Exposure:** If mates are native speakers or advanced learners, they can introduce cultural aspects of the language.

In spite of all these activities students can face some negative factors such as:

1. **Lack of seriousness:** Some students may focus more on socializing rather than learning;

2. **Use of native language:** Friends might prefer speaking in their first language instead of practicing the new one.

3. **Fear of mistakes:** Some students may feel shy or embarrassed to speak in front of friends.

In the process of the work on the pupil's acquiring the knowledge in target language the teacher and parents should help him/her maintain balance. **Extroverts** are much more open to learning than introverts and are never shy about asking

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questions or asking for clarification on something they don't understand. **Introverts**, on the other hand, tend to look up the answer to a grammatical rule or phrase they don't understand in a book or on the internet. Asking questions to students who are more introverted than extroverted without warning or suddenly is likely to startle them and cause them to become confused, which is a bad approach and can cause the student to lose interest when they feel uncomfortable in front of the class.

Now we shall examine some of the factors that motivate pupils:

1. Introverted students benefit from studying at their own pace using self-study materials such as books, apps, or online courses. Writing activities engage the introverted student in journaling, essay writing, or creative writing helps them express their thoughts without the pressure of speaking. Small group discussions help working in pairs or small groups creates a more comfortable environment compared to participating in large group conversations. Technology-based learning and digital tools, including language-learning apps and recorded pronunciation exercises, allow them to practice privately. Listening and reading activities by audiobooks, podcasts, and literature provide effective ways for introverts to absorb the language in a quiet setting. Encouragement without pressure and gradual confidence-building strategies help them develop speaking skills without the stress of addressing large groups.

2. Extroverted students benefit from debates, discussions, and presentations and express their thoughts verbally. Group activities such as role-playing exercises, team projects, and peer conversations sustain their engagement in language learning. Language games, competitions, and interactive activities increase their enthusiasm for learning. Real-life practice conversations with native speakers and participation in language clubs enhance their communicative skills.

Interactive tools such as videos, live discussions, and immersion experiences provide an engaging learning atmosphere. Recognition and rewards, that is the positive feedback, certificates, and small rewards contribute to their motivation and continued effort.

As we have seen from the analysis of the abilities of **introverted** and **extroverted students**, keeping up with the times and keeping up with the latest news is a requirement of today's teaching process. Every day, we are surrounded by very interesting technological innovations. The proper implementation of these innovations into the learning process may be the smartest in the era of globalization and developed digital technologies.

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The research contributes to the theoretical understanding of motivation in language learning, particularly in the context of Uzbekistan. It enriches the existing body of knowledge by integrating socio-cultural perspectives into the analysis of motivational factors. The findings of this research offer practical value by providing actionable insights for educators and curriculum developers. The recommendations can be used to design motivational strategies, teaching methods, and learning environments that are specifically tailored to the needs of upper-grade Uzbek learners, ultimately improving their English language acquisition outcomes.

References:

1. Brown David N. Language Learner Motivative and the Role of Choice in ESP Listening Engagement. Asp: Academic Science Press, 2007, pp.159-177.
2. Dornyei Z. Motivation in Action towards a Process-Oriented Conceptualization of Student Motivation. British Journal of Educational Psychology, 2000, pp.519-538.
3. Eysenck H.J. Extraversion-Introversion Theory. Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences. 2016, pp.1-3.
4. Gardner.R.C. and Lambert W.E. Attitude and Motivation in Second Language Learning. Rowley,MA: Newbury House Publishers, 1972.
5. Graham C.R. "Blended Learning Systems" in the Handbook of Blended Learning. Pfeiffer Publishing, San Francisco, 2006, pp.3-21.
6. Noels Kimberly A., Pelletier Luc G., Clement Richard and Vallerand Robert J. Motivational Orientations and Self- Determination Theory. Journal: Language Learning. 50(S1), 2000, pp.57-85.
7. Ryan Richard M. and Deci Edward L. Self-Determination Theory. University of Rochester. Journal: American Psychologist, 2000.
8. Vygotsky Lev. Theory of Cognitive Development. Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 1978.
9. Warschauer Mark. Computer Assisted Language Learning: An Introduction. Multimedia language teaching, Tokyo: Logos International: pp. 3-20.